

THE PREOPERATIONAL PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Dadakhonova Mohlaroyim Muratvayevna

Andijan state institute of foreign languages

13.00.08 faculty of theory and methodology of preschool education

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Annotation. The preschool age, typically defined as the period between 3 to 5 years, is a crucial developmental stage characterized by rapid growth in various psychological domains. Understanding the psychological characteristics of preschool-aged children is essential for educators, parents, and psychologists as it provides insights into their cognitive, emotional, social, and physical development. Moreover explores the key psychological characteristics of preschool-aged children, highlighting their cognitive development, psychological characteristics, social interactions, and the impact of environmental factors on their growth.

Key words: preschool age, crucial development, psychological domains, cognitive, emotional, social, physical development, psychological characteristics, psychological characteristics, social interactions.

Аннотация. Дошкольный возраст, обычно определяемый как период от 3 до 5 лет, является важнейшей стадией развития, характеризующейся быстрым ростом в различных психологических областях. Понимание психологических характеристик детей дошкольного возраста имеет важное значение для педагогов, родителей и психологов, поскольку оно дает представление об их когнитивном, эмоциональном, социальном и физическом развитии. Кроме того, исследуются ключевые психологические характеристики детей дошкольного возраста, подчеркивая их когнитивное развитие, психологические характеристики, социальные взаимодействия и влияние факторов окружающей среды на их рост.

Ключевые слова: дошкольный возраст, важнейшее развитие, психологические области, когнитивное, эмоциональное, социальное, физическое развитие, психологические характеристики, психологические характеристики, социальные взаимодействия.

Izoh. Odatda 3 yoshdan 5 yoshgacha bo'lgan davr sifatida belgilanadigan maktabgacha yosh, turli xil psixologik sohalarida tez o'sish bilan tavsiflangan muhim rivojlanish bosqichidir. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning psixologik xususiyatlarini tushunish pedagoglar, ot-onalar va psixologlar uchun juda muhim, chunki u ularning kognitiv, hissiy, ijtimoiy va jismoniy rivojlanishi haqida tushuncha beradi. Bundan tashqari, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning asosiy psixologik xususiyatlarini o'rganadi, ularning kognitiv rivojlanishini, psixologik xususiyatlarini, ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sirini va ularning o'sishiga atrof-muhit omillarining ta'sirini yoritadi.

Kalit so'zlar: maktabgacha yosh, hal qiluvchi rivojlanish, psixologik sohalar, kognitiv, hissiy, ijtimoiy, jismoniy rivojlanish, psixologik xususiyatlar, psixologik xususiyatlar, ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sirlar.

The preoperational stage, occurring between ages 2 and 7, is characterized by the development of symbolic thinking and language, but with limitations in logical reasoning and understanding perspectives other than their own. Children in this stage can represent objects and events through words, pictures, and gestures, engaging in pretend play and

imitation. However, they struggle with conservation tasks and may exhibit egocentrism and centration, focusing on single aspects of a situation while ignoring others.

Key features of the preoperational stage: Children can use symbols (like words, images, or objects) to represent things they can't see or that are not present.

Language skills expand significantly, allowing children to express themselves more fully. Learning language seems like a monumental task for the young child. The world's languages contain thousands of words that can be combined to convey an infinite number of meanings. Children are born without knowing which of the world's languages they must learn. If born in Brazil, they must learn Portuguese; if born in the Philippines, they must learn Tagalog. If born in Belgium or Quebec, or into an immigrant or refugee family, they may need to learn 2 different languages simultaneously. Despite these challenges, most children acquire the fundamentals of language effortlessly in the toddler and preschool years, without formal instruction or explicit feedback. By age 5 years, they have a vocabulary of thousands of words; create sentences with complex grammatical features; differentiate literal from nonliteral meanings, such as humor or metaphor; observe the social conventions of conversation; and apply language skills in the service of learning to read. By age 8 years, their speech sound inventory is mature. Variation in the rate and efficiency of language development is substantial. Approximately 16% of children experience delays in the initial phases of language learning, and approximately half of those children show persistent difficulties. (1) In children age 3 to 5 years, speech and language impairment is the most prevalent eligibility criterion that warrants enrollment in special education preschool services (2) Among school-age children, the category of learning disabilities, often a late manifestation of language and speech disorders, predominates as the eligibility criterion for special education; however, speech-language impairment ranks second. Deficits in language or speech that are sufficiently severe to interfere with daily functioning, including learning, communication, and/or social interactions, meet the criteria for a disability. Pediatric clinicians are on the front line for primary, secondary, and tertiary prevention of language and speech disorders. (3) Primary prevention, such as immunizations, prevents the condition from ever occurring. Secondary prevention requires early detection and treatment of a disorder to result in a milder variant than would have. Among the more than 750,000 children in the United States age 3 to 5 years in 2016 who were enrolled in special education services, this pie chart shows the percentages found eligible for services based on speech-language impairment, autism, developmental delays, and other criteria. Speech-language impairment is the most common reason that children are deemed eligible for preschool special education services. based on "parallel distributed processing" or "connectionist frameworks" that are designed to mimic characteristics of human brain structure and function.(5) Basic processing units in these models are simple and highly interactive, analogous to neurons in the brain. Units that become active simultaneously develop connections, and connections that occur in unison form networks. Knowledge is conceptualized as patterns of activity within the network; learning represents changes in the patterns of activity within and across networks. Importantly, networks do not require any initial biases or built-in organization to become organized. Rather, they organize based on experiences in the environment. These models can explain how infants learn whatever language they are exposed to. These models have also been found to further explain many of the phenomena of language learning, such as how children learn to correctly conjugate both regular verbs and irregular verbs. (5)A challenge

for the infant is segmenting the sound stream into meaningful units, such as words, that serve as inputs for learning. Children use “statistical learning” for this purpose. Statistical properties of sound sequences vary. For example, sounds that occur within words have a higher frequency of co-occurrence than sounds that occur between words. Infants as young as age 8 months unconsciously detect these distributional statistical properties and use them to segment the continuous sound stream into word like units. (6) Sequential statistical learning also allows the young child to detect sequential ordering and co-occurrence of words within sentences to explain the acquisition of syntax. (7) Moreover, infants and children can take advantage of statistics of word referent co-occurrences to learn the meanings of words. (8) Statistical learning is facilitated when parents use child-directed language, colloquially known as baby talk. Child-directed language is characterized by limited vocabulary, short sentences, multiple repetitions, relatively few errors, and exaggerated intonation. (9) An important ingredient for language learning is the social context. Early language learning requires human interactions; televisions and computers are not sufficient. Warm, mutually respectful, low-stress exchanges between infants and competent language users (adults or other children) facilitate learning. Language learning requires the child’s active engagement with the input. Children must monitor the input, detecting, for example, differences between what they heard and what they might have said or what they thought a word meant. Recognition of the discrepancy helps children progress in learning semantics and syntax. Talking about what a child is doing or expanding what a child has just said facilitates the child’s active engagement. Another challenge for the infant is learning to map speech perception to speech production. (10) Most of the structures that generate speech sounds in the vocal tract are hidden from view. “Mirror neurons” that fire both when an individual performs an action and when the individual perceives others performing the same action are plausible mechanisms for linking perception to production. Human mirror neuron populations seem to be clustered in several cortical areas in the brain, including the prefrontal cortex, that are often implicated in language use. (10) Primary prevention of language and speech delays or disorders may be achieved by providing children with a rich language environment within positive social relationships. Therefore, recommendations that primary care clinicians can give to parents of infants and young toddlers are as follows: Speak often to infants and young children. Baby talk—the use of simple sentences with exaggerated intonation—is well suited to children’s learning needs.

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